

ISOLATION OF MAGNESIUM COMPOUNDS FROM LOCAL DOLOMITE RAW MATERIALS

Xurramova Sarvinoz Erkin qizi

Termez Institute of Engineering and Technology

Master's student of the second stage of Chemical Technology.

Doʻrmonova Sayyora Soatovna

Teacher of Termiz Institute of Engineering and Technology.

Abstract. Thermal decomposition of magnesium and calcium carbonates, magnesium hydroxide and oxysalts, hydration of magnesium and calcium oxides, precipitation of magnesium hydroxide from solutions of magnesium nitrate and magnesium sulfate with ammonia, systematic study of the interaction of magnesium oxides and hydroxide with salt solutions, potassium hydrosulfate, potassium chloride with potassium-forming sulfuric acid, physical and chemical bases for the processing of non-traditional raw materials (dolomites from local mines and dolomite magnesites) into pure oxides and other magnesium compounds, which significantly expand the raw material base for magnesium production, are being formed and allow solving an important national economic problem. This article presents a technology for extracting magnesium compounds from local dolomite raw materials.

Key words: Dolomite, magnesium nitrate hexahydrate, mass fraction, magnesium oxide, calcium oxide, magnesia additive, carbonization, quenching, precipitation, calcination, quartz impurities, calcite impurities, gypsum impurities, clay.

Аннотация. Термическое разложение карбонатов магния и кальция, гидроксид магния и оксисолей, гидратация оксидов магния и кальция, осаждение гидроксида магния из растворов нитрата и сульфата магния аммиаком, систематическое изучение взаимодействия оксидов магния и гидроксида с растворами солей, гидросульфата калия, хлористый калий с калийобразующей серной кислотой, физико-химические основы переработки нетрадиционного сырья (доломиты местных рудников и доломитовые магнезиты) в чистые оксиды и другие соединения магния, значительно расширяющие сырьевую базу производства магния складывается и позволяет решить важную народнохозяйственную проблему. В данной статье представлена технология извлечения соединений магния из местного доломитового сырья.

Ключевые слова: Доломит, гексагидрат нитрата магния, массовая доля, оксид магния, оксид кальция, магнезиальная добавка, карбонизация, гашение, осаждение, прокаливание, примеси кварца, примеси кальцита, примеси гипса, глина.

Introduction.

To obtain granulated ammonium nitrate that does not harden during long-term storage in warehouses, both in bags and in bulk, a conditioning additive of magnesium nitrate is introduced into the ammonium nitrate solution before granulation, which can be added in an anhydrous state. Up to six water molecules form magnesium nitrate hexahydrate – $Mg(NO_3)_2 \times 6H_2O$. The most common magnesium compounds are volcanogenic formations - primary silicate and aluminosilicate rocks. Secondary solid minerals and natural solutions are usually used as raw materials for the production of magnesium compounds. Soluble magnesium salts and their solutions (waters of the sea and salt lakes), marine sedimentary rocks - dolomites, magnesites and secondary, predominantly hydrated silicates - serpentines, asbestos, talc.

Literature analysis and methodology.

Ferghana Valley (Shorsu) is a dolomite mine in Uzbekistan. Studies of dolomite deposits show that the amount of magnesium compounds in raw materials is lower than in other deposits of the CIS countries. The average content of magnesium compounds on magnesium oxide ranges

from 9 to 20%. In science, various methods are known for extracting magnesium compounds from dolomite and using raw materials and semi-finished products for various branches of the chemical industry. Today, dolomite is widely used in the cement, construction and ceramic industries. Taking into account the localization of imported raw materials, semi-finished products and the use of natural resources in our republic, there is a great interest in dolomite. Dolomite is lumps of various shapes and sizes. In the total mass, in addition to large pieces, there are many small ones, part of dolomite in the form of a powder. The color of the pieces is from light gray to light pink.

Results.

The composition of the original dolomite:

- mass fraction of magnesium in MgO	16.7-17.05%
- mass fraction of calcium CaO	26.09 -31.4%
- mass fraction of acid-insoluble residue	1.22-4.2%
- mass fraction of oxides (III) R ₂ O ₃	0.11 - 0.28%
- mass fraction of sulfates SO ₄ ⁻²	6.22 - 8.26%
- mass fraction of moisture	8.12 - 12.8%

Theoretically, when placing the suspension after quenching, magnesium hydroxide should be in the upper layer due to the difference in molecular weight, which allows magnesium to be coarsely separated from other solid components.

Quenching is carried out at a temperature of 95-100°C to obtain relatively large crystals of Mg(OH)₂ in suspension.

According to the literature data, during the carbonization of a hardened dolomite suspension at an elevated pressure of 5 atm. At the first stage, carbonization of calcium hydroxide at a temperature of 40-60°C with carbon dioxide occurs according to the reaction:

Conclusion.

During the firing of dolomite, carbon dioxide is released, magnesium and calcium are converted into oxides. So, at a temperature of 800°C, the mass fraction of magnesium in MgO increases by 2.45–2.8%, the mass fraction of calcium in CaO by 5–10.31%, and at 1100°C, the mass fraction of magnesium increases. 9.63-9.98%, the mass fraction of calcium increases by 0.14-5.45%.

100 g of crushed dolomite are mixed with 130 cm³ of distilled water and left for 17-18 hours. The sediment is carefully divided into three layers. Each serving is analyzed for calcium and magnesium content.

References:

1. Костанян Р.К., Карамян Г.Г., Ивашкин П.И., Калугин М.М., Мартоян Г.А. Перспективы использование магния в качестве возобновляемого источника энергии. - 2017. М.
2. Хузиахметов Р.Х., Хуснутдинов В.А., Сайфуллин Р.С. Кинетика разложения гидроксосульфата и гидроксохлорида магния в неизотермическом режиме // Изв. вузов. Химияихим. технология.- 1992. Т. 35, вып.3. - С. 77 - 80.
3. Yabe T., Suzuki Y. and Saloh Y. Renewable Energy Cycle with Magnesium and Solar-Energy-Pumped Lasers, Renewable Energy & Power Quality Journal, Vol.1, No12, April 2014, paper 236.
4. Hahn R., Mainert J., Glaw F., Lang K.-D. Sea water magnesium fuel cell power supply, Journal of Power Sources, vol.288, paper 26-35. Aug. 2015.